

The Experience of English Universities in Using Benchmarking and the Possibility of Benefiting from It in Saudi Universities

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Abstract

The present research aims at clarifying how to use benchmarking as an input for developing the performance of Saudi universities in light of the English experience, through identifying the intellectual foundations of comparative measurement and analyzing one of the global models of benchmarking in university education in England. In order to achieve the goals of the study, the descriptive approach was utilized and several results were reached, the most important of which are good planning for applying the methodology of comparative measurement by first starting to publish a culture of comparative measurement before proceeding to the actual application of it, searching for best good practices, and then applying them, with the aim of improving university activities. Benchmarking requires a kind of continuous interaction and cooperation between universities participating in the process, as well as individuals involved in the evaluation of the performance of universities, both inside and outside the university.

1. Introduction

Benchmarking is becoming a central instrument for improving the performance of higher education institutions. Different approaches to higher education benchmarking have been adopted in many countries worldwide. If taken seriously and deployed properly, benchmarking can help colleges and universities position themselves for the new competitive environment. Benchmarking is considered one of the most important modern approaches used by institutions to compare themselves with other institutions that are competing or excelling in a specific field and that can be considered leading institutions. Data on similar processes with others is called practice and do, performing a gap analysis of performance in the sense of examination and evaluation. The scheme ends with the application of solutions or what is known as implementation, and the comparative measurement focuses on the method of performance and not results and provides a true standard for judging the process, by comparing with the best practices available to competitors in the same field (Levy G. & Ronco S, 2012).

Benchmarking seeks out, internalizes, and improves upon competitors' best-practice capabilities. It has been widely utilized in all industrial and service organizations alike, and universities resort to this method in order to evaluate their position compared to the best applications and practices in their field. Today, universities face more than ever endless desires for their beneficiaries, given the knowledge and information revolution, so they strive to meet these desires and face the aging of their services through continuous improvement, monitoring outstanding performance and best practices for their counterparts, adapting their positive aspects, and implementing them to provide better products and services, not for the sake of competition or race, but for the sake of improving their performance to the point of excellence and leadership (Katarzyna, A, 2015).

Benchmarking has emerged in the world of (business) organizations together with some other innovations, especially the "quality movement". The organized attention for quality and benchmarking shares an interest in the organization's performance. The need to apply benchmarking to university education institutions has increased due to the increased desire to improve the quality of services provided by those institutions, the need to compete with distinguished models of prestigious university institutions such as English models, and the effectiveness of the process of comparative measurement of the best in qualifying university institutions to meet the successive challenges that accompanied the community due to various knowledge and repercussions and the increasing need to highlight the competitive advantage of educational institutions and to preserve their role in society (Rezić, S., et al., 2012)

Institutions benchmarking in such universities seems natural as it is the inherent feature of universities to practice and propagate learning. Therefore, higher education institutions (HEIs) should exercise and improve

their ability to learn from the best in order to improve the whole institution itself which imposed the necessity of using comparative measurement of the best in an effective way and benefiting from the experiences of the prestigious university institutions by answering some questions, including: Where are we in relation to others? How can we use the methods of those university institutions? How can we achieve more distinction than those university institutions? (Nazarko, J.; Kuźmicz, K. A, 2009).

Aims:

The main objective of the current research is to clarify how to use comparative measurement as an input to develop the performance of Saudi universities in light of the English experience, through identifying the intellectual foundations of comparative measurement and analyzing one of the global models of comparative measurement in university education in England.

The Importance of the Research and Its Justifications:

The following points represent the importance of the current research:

- 1- Its approach to one of the recent trends in the field of university administration, which is comparative measurement, being an effective tool for developing the performance of universities.
- 2- Increasing interest in achieving quality in the Saudi university education institutions in order to achieve the Kingdom's 2030 vision and seeking to distinguish the outcomes of Saudi universities.
- 3- Trying to direct the attention of those responsible for developing university education in the Kingdom towards the importance of employing comparative measurement of the best in developing the overall performance of university institutions by comparing Saudi universities with their counterparts in developed countries and benefiting from their experiences in developing Saudi university education.

Methodology:

The current research depends on the descriptive approach in achieving its goals, answering its questions, and addressing its scientific axes because it analyzes, describes, and explains the reality or phenomenon under study.

Limitations:

Limitations of the current research include the following:

- **Objective Limitations:** The current research focuses on comparative measurement as an approach to achieve the development of the performance of Saudi universities, and it deals with one of the global models of comparative measurement, which is represented in university education in England.
- **Geographical Limitations:** The research was limited to dealing with comparative measurement in England as a global model that can be used to develop the performance of Saudi universities.
- **Time Limitations:** The research attempted to deal with comparative measurement of the best and its stages of development in English universities, until the present time.

Terms:

Definitions of benchmarking vary widely, from the practical "a self-improvement tool for organizations which allows them to compare themselves with others, to identify their comparative strengths and weaknesses and learn how to improve. Benchmarking is a way of finding and adopting best practices" to the participative "the open and collaborative evaluation of services and processes with the aim of emulating best available practice" through to the global and ambitious.

Benchmarking is also defined as an ongoing, systematic process for measuring and comparing the work processes of one organization or department to those of another by bringing an external focus to internal activities, functions, or operations. The goal of benchmarking is to provide key personnel in charge of processes with an external standard for measuring the quality and cost of internal activities and to help identify where opportunities for improvement may reside (Paliulis, N. & Labanauskis, R, 2015).

It is also seen as a standard way to collect and report important procedural data, in a way that helps in making appropriate comparisons between aspects of performance in university institutions or programs, with the aim of achieving good practice, diagnosing problems that hinder performance, and identifying areas of strength (Seybert, J. A., Weed, E. J., and Bers, T. H, 2012).

Therefore, it is possible to define the comparative measurement with the best procedural in this research as a codified scientific process through which the performance of university institutions is compared with their best performing counterparts with the aim of benefiting from them in developing the performance of those institutions.

The Intellectual Framework for a Comparative measurement of University Education in Light of Contemporary Educational Literature:

Benchmarking is one of the entry points to quality assurance when comparing one institution to another in some aspects of performance. It includes processes, products, and services, with the aim of finding information on these aspects that one institution excels in and finding a way through which the level of quality and performance could be improved. The mechanisms of comparative measurement include two types, the first of which is the strategic mechanism that emphasizes what has been accomplished and includes the administrative strategy and

the structure, and the second is the procedural mechanism that focuses on moving from what has been accomplished to how the work is performed (Snježana Rezić, et al., 2014).

The basics of comparative measurement in university education can be addressed as follows:

The Concept of Benchmarking:

In an increasingly competitive higher education environment, paralleled by national and European governments calls for reforms at both system and institutional levels, improving university performance has become of paramount importance to demonstrate accountability for the use of public funding, quality of education and research, and contribution to economic growth. National governments are gathering all types of data to support policy, strategic development, and restructure of their higher education systems.

Benchmarking is considered one of the most important and strongest methods on which educational institutions can rely in measuring and improving quality. Several labels have emerged for the concept of comparative measurement, among which: model calibration, reference comparison, benchmarking, comparative measurement, measurement with others, improvement criteria, and improvement, but they all agree that we have one concept, which is continuous improvement, improvement through learning from others, and “taking advantage of all that is new, in a way that suits the circumstances and capabilities of each entrepreneur”.

Benchmarking represents an ongoing process to search for best practices, including an aspect of learning from others with a view to development and not just evaluation, which is one of the stages of implementing comprehensive quality programs and is one of its most important components. “This process includes looking outside the organization, industry, region, or country to learn how others achieve a good level of performance and to understand the processes that are used to achieve it. In this way, comparative measurement helps to know the reasons behind outstanding performance” (Blakeman, J., 2002).

Benchmarking is often described as a systematic and continuous process (Camp (1994), Zairi (1994), Cook (1995), and Murphy (1995)). It aims to identify, measure, compare, adopt, and implement best practices. Epper (1999), for example, describes benchmarking as “a systematic way of learning from others and changing what you do” (p. 26). According to her, benchmarking starts with self-examination and understanding of the different functions and internal procedures of an institution in order to be able to look for the best practices in other institutions and finally adapt them to improve performance as presented in Figure (1). Nazarko et al. (2009) identify learning as the most indispensable and important pillar of benchmarking which they define as a continuum process encompassing both the identification of best practices and their adaptation. They also stress the importance of the creative adaptation of the best practices without copying and the continuity of the process.

Figure 1: Benchmarking process, Nazarko et al. (2009).

Benchmarking is also known as a continuous process of comparison, drawing plans, and effective application, as it includes comparing the institution and its internal activities with the best institutions regardless of its activity, comparing the performance of the various operations of the institution with distinguished operations in similar institutions with the aim of reaching the best value, and comparing different types of

performance improvement methods to choose the method that has best value and that is appropriate to be applied with the circumstances of each institution (Tasopoulou, K. & Tsiotras, G, 2017).

Through the previous definitions, it is obvious that comparative measurement is one of the quality methods used to improve the performance by comparing the performance of the university institution with that of better institutions in light of specific scientific criteria. This enables the university institution to diagnose problems that hinder its performance and to identify its strengths.

Benchmarking Objectives:

Benchmarking aims at developing the performance of institutions of various activities and is a tool for improvement and excellence through observing the best methods and finding ideas and sources for improvement from inside and outside the institutions. Bender emphasizes that comparative measurement greatly affects the decisions of the organization and helps in its formation through analyzing the best practices. For the corresponding institutions and developing programs accordingly, the most important objectives pursued by comparative measurement can be identified as follows.

According to Joo et al. (2011), benchmarking has the following main goals:

- 1- Helping to change the organizational culture and direct it towards a culture of continuous improvement, supporting innovations, and learning from best practices.
- 2- Looking at it as an administrative input used by the institutions to evaluate their performance and a way to improve their operations and practices.
- 3- Relying on the continuous search for best practices because superior institutions are constantly changing.
- 4- Helping in planning and setting strategic goals in light of analyzing and studying competitors' strategies, requirements, and aspirations of beneficiaries of education and the possibility of university education institutions.
- 5- Constantly pursuing partnership between competitors, with the aim of exchanging information in order to improve performance.
- 6- Continuous improvement of all educational and administrative activities, products, services, and practices, and hence the overall performance of the university institution.
- 7- Directing improvement efforts towards the most important areas that reflect the critical success factors in light of the goals of open university education institutions, including universities that offer open education programs.

The Importance of Benchmarking:

The pioneering institutions that wish to persist in their work and to achieve distinction and creativity must always work on improving their performance in comparison to the performance of competitors and the performance of the leading institutions in the field of the institution's work. Since benchmarking is one of the methods that help the organization to know its level of performance compared to the performance of its competitors, and since it is a method for continuous improvement, its importance is evident through the benefits achieved, which can be identified as follows:

- 1- Assists the institution in accurately identifying the gap between its performance and the performance of leading institutions in its field of work.
- 2- Helps to provide the appropriate climate and enhances the desire of the leadership of the institution and its workers to adopt a policy of change towards everything that is better and new.
- 3- Helps to define critical operations and gives them the necessary attention and priority in implementation.
- 4- Actively contributes to developing individual and collective creativity.
- 5- Actively contributes to increasing the possibilities of achieving additional benefits for the organization.

Benchmarking Properties and Components:

The comparative measurement has several characteristics as follows (Krishnamoorthy, Bala & D'Lima, Christine, 2014):

- 1- Helps to change the organizational culture and direct it towards a culture of continuous improvement, supporting innovations, and learning from best practices.
- 2- Is an administrative input that organizations use to evaluate their performance and a way to improve their operations and practices.
- 3- Relies on the constant search for best practices because superior institutions are constantly changing.
- 4- Helps to plan and set strategic goals in light of analyzing and studying competitors' strategies, requirements, and aspirations of beneficiaries of education and the possibility of university education institutions.
- 5- Constantly pursues partnership between competitors, with the aim of exchanging information in order to improve performance.

- 6- Continuously improves all educational and administrative activities, products, services, and practices, and hence the overall performance of the university institution.
- 7- Directs improvement efforts towards the most important areas that reflect the critical success factors in light of the goals of open university education institutions, including universities that offer open education programs.

It is clear from the above that the multiplicity of comparative measurement features with the best, even if it can be crystallized in investing best practices and applications in different fields of distinguished university institutions, in addition to being an approach used to measure performance and to identify shortcomings towards the application of the best methods that lead to the continuous improvement of institutions wishing to improve. The UK Higher Education International Standards Agency report indicates that international comparisons are useful only inasmuch as it informs the relevant business decisions for improving strategic performance. It follows from this view that institutional approaches to benchmarking should be contingent on the current objectives, status, and priorities of individual institutions. This suggests a four-stage, strategy-contingent benchmarking model, as illustrated here (Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2011):

(Higher Education Statistics Agency, 2011, p.29)

Principles of Benchmarking for the Best in University Education:

The best analogy is based on some principles as follows (Jackson, Norman & Lund, Helen. (2000):

- Organizing: It is considered a structured approach to improving work. It searches for the best practice and method for doing something and then applies it, with the aim of improving a specific activity to reach an index that exceeds the current performance index.
- Cooperation: The comparative measurement requires a kind of continuous interaction and cooperation between the universities participating in the process, as well as individuals involved in evaluating the performance of universities, both inside and outside the university.
- Comparison: It is a process of comparing one institution with other institutions with outstanding performance, with the aim of finding modern approaches and new ideas.
- Continuity: It is a continuous process of comparison and measurement, for entrepreneurs anywhere in the world, in order to gain knowledge that helps the organization in improving its performance and to compare operations and similar activities between institutions and fields of work, so that opportunities for improvement can be identified.
- Measurement and evaluation: It attempts to measure the degree of the institution's evaluation towards achieving a specific goal and a good competitive position for it in the future.
- Defining clearly the work steps: It focuses on identifying and understanding the alignment of superior practices of other institutions anywhere in the world and their application within the institution in order to improve its performance.
- Ongoing division: It focuses on continuous and systematic evaluation of services and business functions of institutions versus the performance of other organizations.
- Inclusivity: It is a comprehensive and integrated approach that seeks the participation of all parties in the process of continuous improvement of the institution's activity, and it represents innovative ways of working that contribute to the improvement of performance.
- The future dimension of the evaluation: It emphasizes the need for the institution's administration to evaluate its intellectual assets from working individuals and set a strategic plan that includes defining its current and future needs of human capital with scientific competence.

From the above, it can be observed that achieving the principles of comparative measurement requires the necessity of having some kind of positive trend among universities and their members towards the comparison process and understanding the expectations of their internal and external clients related to the fields of development. It is also necessary for the university institutions wishing to improve their performance to deal with these issues according to a scientific method based on a detailed analysis of operations and enterprise practices.

Types of Benchmarking:

The Union for Excellence in Higher Education defines benchmarking as a group of different types as follows (Pulatkhan, L, 2007):

1. The internal comparative measurement: It is done by comparing specific groups or sectors within the university with groups or other sectors within the same university. It is characterized by helping in gaining knowledge and collective learning at the university in question. In addition to that, it provides consistency and stability with regard to the conduct of operations and procedures within them.
2. The external comparative measurement: In this type, a comparison is made between two or more universities with respect to a specific service or a specific process. Among the advantages of this type of comparative measurement, it is considered a useful way to determine the points of measurement and comparison within the university, and it makes use of the information generated from the comparison process for the purposes of planning and drawing the university strategy.
3. The functional comparative measurement: In this type, the prominent leaders at the university level who occupy similar jobs are identified, and the best among them is identified, with a suggestion of all possible ways to eliminate performance gaps and improve operations.
4. The comprehensive comparative measurement: It is based on making comparisons related to the processes and procedures implemented by the university, which are useful in identifying distinguished universities.

Benchmarking Processes:

Some researchers indicate that benchmarking processes are planning, researching, observing, analyzing, and adapting (Nazarko, et al., 2009), while others state that the methodology of comparative measurement is carried out according to five processes that can be mentioned as follows:

Developed by the author based on Nazarko, et al. (2009)

Benchmarking Steps in University Education:

The best comparative measurement steps can be addressed as follows (Seybert, J., Weed, E. & Bers, T, 2012):

1. Choosing the field of application: The focus should be on the areas that are most important to the recipients of the services (internally and externally) and the most important areas that are expected to be successful in the application are chosen.
2. Choosing the comparison method used: There are two methods for applying the comparative measurement:
 - Choosing a university institution and participating with it in exchanging information for comparative measurement.
 - Involving an external agency responsible for selecting the best educational institutions in the chosen field of application and collecting the necessary information. This type is considered to require less effort, as the burden of choice is placed on the external party, but it is more expensive except for that government.
3. Analysis of the processes chosen for the application: The processes are analyzed by identifying the components and elements of each process in light of the needs of the beneficiary of the educational service.
4. Evaluating and reviewing the collected information: This includes the cost of the application and understanding of the relationship between efficiency and cost, so that the best educational institutions that achieve the highest quality satisfying the beneficiary at the lowest possible cost and achieve credibility by comparing the different applications of the institutions in light of the specified criteria are chosen.
5. Defining the gap: The gap is determined by comparing the methods of implementing the operations of the educational institution in which the study is taking place and the other institution with outstanding performance.
6. Implementation of a plan: A plan is to be implemented with the aim of improving and developing the selected operations, to be prepared in an innovative way.

Benchmarking of English Universities

The History of Comparative Measurement and Its Development Stages:

The beginning of Benchmarking in England dates back to 1964 when the British Higher Education was subject to examination by the Council of National Academic Awards, which was formed with the aim of quality control and standards. Moreover, in the period from 1984 to 1986 AD, there was an urgent need for introducing formal systems for quality assurance in universities, which gradually moved from the National Academic Awards Council to individual institutions (Jackson, Norman, 2001).

The emergence of comparative measurement in England was not a sudden matter, but rather was the result of a set of policies that targeted the development of education, which began with the mid-1985s and attempted to provide the necessary funding for universities, provide a kind of educational accounting within them, and encourage the British university institutions to improve their productivity in light of a set of performance indicators to know the progress. That was accompanied by the application of some numerical values in measuring the quality of universities as an alternative to simple administrative statistics, which were known as "the comparative measurement of the best" (Lund, H., 1998).

Benchmarking activities in UK higher education (HE) began in the early to mid-1990s. The method was initially applied to the management of services like library, facilities, estates, energy, and treasury. However, interest in the technique has grown rapidly over the last two years to the point where it is likely to become a significant tool for the management and improvement of quality and standards in most areas of HE. There are a number of reasons for this. For instance, successive government policies have attempted to create a more competitive environment. The transformation from a small elitist to a large, multipurpose mass system of higher education has been accomplished by a 30 percent reduction in the unit costs of full-time equivalent students. The need to be efficient and cost-effective, in order to optimize the resources available to support learning, has never been greater. Benchmarking is one method that HE institutes (HEIs) can use to help themselves achieve this objective and to demonstrate to funding councils that they are providing value for the public investment.

Since 1993, English universities have started to develop a set of normative data describing academic standards expected from graduates in specific subject areas (Jackson, N. & Loud, H., 2001). The data that shows what the graduates are expected to know and understand at the end of their studies was developed by specialists. The data has been used as reference points in the design, delivery, and review of academic programs (QAA, 2019). In 1997, reference comparisons focused on the skills graduates acquire from the programs they have studied. This came as a result of the comments of employers who emphasized the need to focus on those skills (QAA, 2015). Since 2000 until now, English universities have started to make reference comparisons with each other to include all aspects and academic standards in order to improve the educational service provided and meet the requirements of the beneficiaries of graduates who possess the skills and capabilities that enable them to carry out the burdens of various jobs required by the country (Nick Hillman, 2018).

The Objectives of Comparative Measurement in English Universities:

The objectives of comparative measurement in English universities include the following (Luiz, C.R., 2002):

- 1- Activating the commitment of English universities to achieve quality and excellence in providing the service.
- 2- The proper application of the institutional evaluation methodology.
- 3- The continuous evaluation of the academic and administrative performance of universities.
- 4- Determining the strengths and weaknesses in the universities' performance.
- 5- Helping universities to develop effective improvement plans.
- 6- Providing a reference framework for the continuous development and improvement of good practices at the university.
- 7- Benefiting from the experiences of the corresponding universities in developing the educational process.
- 8- Helping English universities to predict and plan well for the future.

Principles of Comparative Measurement in English Universities:

The process of comparative measurement of the best in England is based on a set of principles governing the process of comparison and performance evaluation, as follows (Jackson, N. & Loud, H., 2001):

- 1- University institutions need to be creative, in order to gain the ability to respond to external factors in line with international standards.
- 2- Diversity in the programs and curricula they provide.
- 3- Accounting, intellectual, financial, and administrative independence in achieving the quality of education.
- 4- The effectiveness of comparative measurement in achieving a balance between the public and private interests.
- 5- Academic freedom to include the academic freedom of the students and faculty members.

Comparative Measurement Procedures in English Universities:

The process of comparative measurement with preference is carried out in England according to a set of procedures and steps, as follows (Reda Al-Melegy, 2011; Jackson, N. & Loud, H., 2001):

- The stage of developing the basics: At this stage, it is determined whether there is a gap between the current performance of the university institution and the expected performance, and the extent of the existence of practices that contribute to improving the performance of the university institution.
- Choosing the comparative measurement style to be applied: Specific criteria are established to choose the comparative measurement style to be used, and this needs to develop individuals' understanding of the basics of comparative measurement, focus on continuous improvement processes, manage organizational change processes, and bridge the organizational gap.
- Determining the aspects of comparative measurement: At this stage, academic administrative processes are planned, and areas that need to be developed, areas for evaluation, and individuals and entities involved in the evaluation process are identified.
- Setting standards and indicators: This is done in light of existing practices and agreed policies, and defining some criteria and indicators through which the performance of the university institution is evaluated.
- Applying the frameworks and benchmarks: This is done according to a specific strategy or approach, and learning from previous experiences and experiences with the aim of supporting continuous improvement processes.

The recent benchmarking initiatives in the field of research focus on cooperation between universities and enterprises, transfer of research into industry, and common publications. It should be noted that benchmarking is rarely employed in this area although the results of such initiatives would be highly useful and interesting to the stakeholders of HEIs (Kuźmicz, 2015). More and more often the subject of benchmarking involves practices that support the core mission of the university (research and teaching). These practices involve administration and management of the university, including risk management, sustainable development, resources, and supply.

The examples of benchmarking initiatives quoted in this paper embrace initiatives based on cooperation of universities. Higher education institutions create a benchmarking group in the framework of which they learn through making comparisons. Sometimes they engage specialists in benchmarking universities such as Association for Commonwealth Universities (ACU) and Higher Education Academy (HEA) in the UK. Often universities decide on one-to-one benchmarking, which means that they make use of the services of companies specialized in benchmarking which offer a possibility to compare with other HEIs through the use of a database.

Figure 2. Classification of benchmarking initiatives in HEIs (source: on the basis of Kuźmicz)

Lessons from the English Experience:

Among the most prominent lessons learned from the English experience are the following:

- 1- The necessity of universities' commitment to achieving quality and excellence in providing educational services.
- 2- Good preparation for applying the best measurement methodology.
- 3- Analyzing the current conditions of universities to determine the strengths and weaknesses in their performance.
- 4- The need to develop effective improvement plans in light of an objective analysis of the universities' performance.
- 5- Self-assessment of performance.
- 6- Better understanding of the processes which support strategy formulation and implementation in increasingly competitive environments.
- 7- Measurement and comparison with other institutions or organizations and assessment of the reasons for any differences.
- 8- Encouraging discovery of new ideas through a strategic look (inside or outside the institution).
- 9- Obtaining data to support decision-making.
- 10- Setting effective targets for improvement.
- 11- Strengthening the institutional identity, strategy formulation, and implementation.
- 12- Enhancing reputation.
- 13- Responding to national (or international) performance indicators and benchmarks.
- 14- Setting new standards for the institution and sector.
- 15- Benchmarking the university's performance against other higher education institutions allowing the university to get a sense of where it is performing well in relation to others.
- 16- Accounting, intellectual, financial, and administrative independence of universities.
- 17- Setting criteria for evaluating universities' performance.
- 18- Emphasizing the participation of all faculty and individuals working in the university institution in the reference comparison process.
- 19- The possibility of employing comparative measurement as a tool to support further continuous improvement.

Study Recommendations:

The study recommends the following:

- 1- Highlighting benchmarking and its applications at the general education stage.
- 2- Clarifying the relationship between benchmarking and strategic planning in Saudi university institutions.
- 3- Activating the culture of benchmarking with the best among faculty and academic leaders in Saudi universities.
- 4- Analyzing the problems of benchmarking of the best in university education institutions and their proposed solutions.

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